

Open Science NL Advisory Panel on Open Research Software

Meeting Notes

18 June 2024, 15:00-17:00 CEST (UTC + 2:00)

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel Katz (until 16:00 CEST)
- John Swinbank
- Karthik Ram
- Laurents Sesink
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Martine de Vos
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Vincent Traag (from 15.30 CEST)
- Maria Cruz (MC), Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) Co-chair

Apologies

- Daniela Gawehns (DG)
-

Welcome and introductions

MC opened the meeting by thanking panel members for, first of all, applying to become members of the panel and expressing appreciation for their volunteering their time and expertise to Open Science NL and the Open Research Software panel specifically.

MC and MT introduced themselves.

Round of introductions from the advisory panel members

MC introduced DG and subsequently, all panel members introduced themselves with a few slides covering their experience and expertise, the challenges they see in the area of open research software, any potential conflicts of interest and their preferences for a two- or three-year term.

Two types of challenges were stressed independently by several panel members:

1. the need to emphasise the importance of re-use, maintenance and sustainability of research software, and
2. The need to better value and reward contributions to research software as a research output.

Introduction to Open Science NL and the Open Research Software Advisory Panel

MC and MT gave a presentation about Open Science NL and the Open Research Software Panel Advisory Panel (scope and ways of working and future activities of the panel).

Q&A

Several points were discussed/mentioned:

- Open hardware is considered within the scope of the panel;
- How future OSNL funding programmes will be developed and how panel members can contribute to the development;
- [The report of the EOSC Scholarly Infrastructures of Research Software](#) was shared by one of the participants as a useful gap analysis revealing the scholarly infrastructure needs related to research software;
- Ways of working; several panel members indicated that they would be willing to contribute more to the activities than what was described within the terms of reference;
- One panel members expressed their preference not to work with Google drive for privacy reasons. [CryptPad](#) was suggested as a possible alternative, which will be considered by OSNL.

Actions

- MC will analyse people preference's for a two- or three-year term and propose a split to the panel members;
- OSNL will consider alternatives to Google drive and will investigate if it is possible to create a mailing list for the panel;
- OSNL to schedule a meeting in November/December.

Meeting close

MC closed the meeting at 16.50